

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CATALYTIC PYROLYSIS SYSTEMS OF LIGHT HYDROCARBONS

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Abstract

An alternative to thermal pyrolysis is catalytic pyrolysis, which provides a higher conversion of raw materials at a lower temperature than thermal pyrolysis, that is, it reduces the energy intensity of the process and increases the selectivity of pyrolysis for lower alkenes

Keywords: catalytic processes, pyrolysis, pyrolysis process, physical basis of pyrolysis process, chemical basis of pyrolysis process, fragmentation.

Introduction

The most common industrial method of ethylene and propylene production to obtain polymers is the thermal pyrolysis of saturated hydrocarbons in tubular pyrolysis furnaces, which is carried out at a high temperature of 780-900 °C and has a number of significant drawbacks, the main ones being low ethylene yield and a significant amount of soot, accumulation in pyrolysis coils of pyrolysis furnaces, which reduces the mileage between regeneration of the furnaces and the service life of the rolls. At the same time, the time required for reactor degassing operations is almost equal to the time spent on ethylene and propylene production [1].

An alternative to thermal pyrolysis is catalytic pyrolysis, which provides a higher conversion of raw materials at a lower temperature than thermal pyrolysis, that is, it reduces the energy intensity of the process and increases the selectivity of pyrolysis for lower alkenes. A considerable number of studies have been conducted in this area, but the problem of increasing the efficiency of oil refining remains an important task [2].

Pyrolysis – (from the ancient Greek word fire, heat; decomposition) – is the decomposition of organic and many inorganic compounds by heat.

The pyrolysis process is the thermal decomposition of organic materials under the influence of high temperature without access to oxygen. This process results in the breakdown of complex organic compounds into simpler molecules such as hydrocarbons, gases, and carbon-based materials. This process produces solid, liquid, and gaseous products. Pyrolysis is used in a variety of industries, including fuel production, the chemical industry, and the production of various carbon

materials. The use of pyrolysis has expanded to the production of synthetic rubber, which has become an important component in the production of tires and other rubber products.

Pyrolysis generally involves heating the material above its decomposition temperature, breaking the chemical bonds in its molecules. Fragments usually break down into smaller molecules, but can combine to form larger molecular mass residues or even amorphous covalent solids [3, 4].

Many environments may contain some amount of oxygen, water, or other substances, so combustion, hydrolysis, or other chemical processes may occur in addition to pyrolysis. Sometimes these chemicals are added intentionally, such as in wood burning, traditional coal production, and steam cracking of crude oil.

Conversely, the starting material can be heated in vacuum or in an inert atmosphere to avoid adverse chemical reactions. Vacuum pyrolysis also improves by-product recovery by lowering the boiling point [4].

As we know, there are several types of pyrolysis they are as follows.

Dry pyrolysis. Thermal treatment of wastes carried out with this method ensures their highly effective neutralization and use as fuel and chemical raw materials. Dry pyrolysis is a thermal decomposition process performed without the introduction of oxygen. As a result, pyrolysis gas with high combustion temperature, liquid product and solid hydrocarbon residue are obtained. The pyrolysis process varies depending on temperature.

1) Low temperature pyrolysis (450-550 °C). This type of pyrolysis is characterized by the maximum release of liquid and solid residues and the minimum release of pyrolysis gas.

2) Medium temperature pyrolysis (up to 800 °C) or medium temperature coking. It passes through the production of a large amount of gas with a low combustion temperature and a small amount of liquid residue and coke.

3) High temperature pyrolysis or coking (900-1050 °C). In this process, minimal output of liquid and solid products and obtaining gas with a large amount of minimal combustion heat is observed. The obtained gas is suitable for long-distance transport as a high-quality fuel.

Currently, the fields of use of the dry pyrolysis method are expanding, and at the stage of the development of modern science and technology, the use of solid organic waste is one of the methods of separating valuable components from them [5].

Pyrolysis of hydrocarbons. Pyrolysis of hydrocarbons (800-900 °C) process (gas hydrocarbons directly expelling gasoline, gasoil) is the source of obtaining ethylene, propylene, divinylbenzene and other products.

Firewood pyrolysis. As a result of this process (450-500 °C), charcoal, methyl alcohol, acetic acid, acetone, resin, etc. such compounds are obtained.

Pyrolysis of garbage and waste. There are many projects for the destruction of household waste by pyrolysis. Difficulties in organizing the pyrolysis of tires, plastic masses and other organic waste are not related to the technology of this process. Because their pyrolysis does not differ from the thermal processing technology of other solid materials. The problem is that most of the waste contains phosphorus, chlorine and sulfur. Chlorine and organic products of pyrolysis enter into an active reaction and lead to the production of toxic hard-to-decompose substances (dioxin). Removing these compounds from smoke is an expensive and complicated process. polymers are very valuable raw materials, as a result of their low-temperature pyrolysis (500 °C) processing, liquid fractions of hydrocarbons (synthetic oil), hydrocarbon residue (technical carbon) and combustible gas are obtained.

Also, pyrolysis has become a key step in the production of plastics that provide raw materials for hydrocarbon components [6].

In the pyrolysis process, organic raw materials such as wood, coal, oil products or biomass are used. The versatility of the pyrolysis process makes it an object of interest in sustainable resource management, waste reduction and the development of alternative energy sources.

The process of thermal pyrolysis of raw materials (oil and its fractions) is the main method of obtaining low-molecular unsaturated hydrocarbons – olefins (alkenes) – ethylene and propylene.

The average annual increase in the use of ethylene and propylene in the world is more than 4 %. In addition to the production of ethylene and propylene, the pyrolysis of oil is the main source for the production of divinyl obtained from the pyrolysis of the C4 fraction and the rectification of the fractions separated during the removal of benzene from the pyrolysis liquids. In the world, 80 % of butadiene production and 39 % of

benzene production are carried out by pyrolysis of hydrocarbons.

With the increasing awareness of environmental issues in recent decades, pyrolysis processes are recognized as one of the methods that open new perspectives for recycling plastic waste, turning it into fuel or other valuable products, and sustainable waste management.

Today, pyrolysis is widely used to process a variety of hydrocarbon materials, including oil, coal, and even waste, to produce fuels, chemicals, and other valuable materials. Pyrolysis research continues to improve process efficiency and develop new applications.

To date, the only industrial method that has been mastered and is widespread is pyrolysis in tube furnaces. Today, its qualitative development is mainly focused on improving existing technology. However, despite advances in furnace coil and convection zone design and the use of modern quench vaporizers, the capabilities of this process are limited. The need to expand the base of raw materials, to reduce the specific consumption of raw materials, including energy and material costs, makes us look for new modifications of the process. It is mainly designed for pyrolysis of heavy hydrocarbon raw materials (fuel oil, vacuum gas oil, oil). At the same time, fundamentally new methods for pyrolysis are proposed: catalytic, oxidative, hydrogenation, as well as thermal connection options. Scientific research in this area is being carried out very intensively, but even the emergence of the most promising projects has not yet led to a radical revision of the existing technologies of the hot pyrolysis unit. However, some progress has been made in the separation of the process products, making the individual butenes, iso- and n-amylenes, isopentane, isoprene, and dicyclopentadiene more accessible, which can give a sharp impetus to the development of new industrial syntheses based on them. The expansion of the base of raw materials and the range of pyrolysis, according to most forecasts, will maintain its position in the petrochemical industry in the near future [6-8].

Catalytic pyrolysis systems of light hydrocarbons

Pyrolysis of light hydrocarbons is a thermal decomposition process. This method involves exposing hydrocarbons to high temperatures without oxygen. Light hydrocarbons such as methane or ethane serve as raw materials for pyrolysis. The process usually takes place at temperatures ranging from 500 °C to 900 °C. The lack of oxygen prevents combustion and causes the decomposition of hydrocarbons. Pyrolysis yields simpler compounds, such as ethylene, propylene, and other valuable by-products. It is a crucial step in the production of plastics, synthetic rubber, and various chemicals. This method helps convert complex hydrocarbons into more controlled and useful compounds. Pyrolysis is used in petrochemicals and refining. It is widely used for resource optimization in industry. The efficiency of pyrolysis makes it a key component in sustainable and circular economy initiatives.

In petrochemicals, the term “pyrolysis” refers to the process of destructive and targeted conversion of primary hydrocarbons (preferably paraffinic) to lower olefins in the presence of superheated water vapor at temperatures above 750 °C, followed by sharp cooling

of the products to 370-420 °C. It should be noted that this definition of pyrolysis applies only to oil refining. In a broader sense, it is the destructive transformation of raw materials under the influence of high temperature without air intake, for example, pyrolysis of biomass or coal. The base of raw materials for pyrolysis can theoretically be quite wide: associated gas, naphtha, gas oil and even crude oil. However, in practice, the total share of gas raw materials (ethane, propane, butane) and naphtha exceeds 90 %.

If mainly ethylene is obtained from associated gas, then pyrolysis of heavier raw materials from naphtha allows to additionally obtain a very valuable set of hydrocarbons – propylene, benzene, butadiene, isoprene, isobutylene, butenes, isoamylenes, acetylene.

The presence of three main and largest capacity compounds among the products of a process – ethylene, propylene and benzene – once again emphasizes the uniqueness of the pyrolysis process. It is these products that constitute the raw energy base of the petrochemical industry, and currently their annual production is one of the bases of the industrial potential of a specific region [8].

The most common industrial method of propylene and ethylene production process to produce polymers is thermal pyrolysis of saturated hydrocarbons in tubular pyrolysis furnaces, which is carried out at high temperatures of 780-900 °C, and this process has several significant drawbacks.

An alternative to thermal pyrolysis is the catalytic pyrolysis process, which provides a higher conversion of raw materials at a lower temperature than thermal pyrolysis, which means that it reduces the energy intensity of the process and increases the selectivity of pyrolysis for lower alkenes. Almost a large number of research works have been carried out in this field, but the problem of increasing the efficiency of oil refining remains an important task. The search for new efficient catalytic systems allows to reduce the temperature of the pyrolysis process and to increase the selectivity of the process for ethylene and electroexplosive destruction tubes. Metallic and bimetallic conductors Ag, Al, Cu, Fe, Ni, Ti, Pt, W, Mo.

Physico-chemical basis of pyrolysis

Unsaturated hydrocarbons, which are the target products of the pyrolysis process, are thermodynamically more stable than the corresponding paraffins only when sufficiently high temperatures are reached. For example, this value for ethylene is 750 °C. Let us compare the thermodynamics of the possible ways of formation of olefins. In the first case, during the splitting (cracking) of the original paraffin molecule:

secondly, during dehydrogenation:

where ΔG^0T – isobar isothermal potential, which is a measure of the thermodynamic possibility of a process. While ΔG^0

$T \leq 0$, the reaction is possible.

For both routes, it is thermodynamically favorable to increase the temperature and decrease the pressure, but the main thing is the cracking of the hydrocarbon chain, and the contribution of the dehydrogenation reaction to the formation of pyrolysis products is noticeable only after reaching 800-850 °C (Fig. 1).

Thus, the main pyrolysis reaction (especially when oil fractions are used as raw materials) is the cracking of the hydrocarbon chain with the formation of olefin and paraffin (Fig. 1, route I). Its main products can undergo further cracking (secondary cracking – routes II and III). The end result is a mixture of light hydrocarbons rich in olefins.

Dehydrogenation of the corresponding olefins leads to the formation of acetylene and its derivatives, as well as butadiene and other highly reactive diene hydrocarbons (IV). The latter, under pyrolysis conditions, undergoes cyclization or Diels Alder (V) reactions. During dehydrogenation, arenes are obtained from cycloolefins, especially benzene (VI), which in turn are precursors of polycyclic hydrocarbons and coke (VII).

The occurrence of the latter reactions (and therefore the increase in coke deposition) is favorable with an increase in temperature to 900-1000 °C. The radical chain mechanism of cracking has been proven for a long time (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The main route of pyrolysis

Primary free radicals are not stable. In the case of naphtha pyrolysis, their stabilization mainly occurs due to the cleavage of the C-C bond located in the β position to the radical center, which corresponds to the general principle of the least structural change:

This β cleavage reaction is repeated until a relatively stable radical is formed – methyl or ethyl, which in turn becomes the source of nucleation of a new chain.

The probability of formation of certain radicals in the chain continuation stage depends on the structure of the hydrocarbon molecule under attack.

Separation of a hydrogen atom from a tertiary carbon atom occurs more easily than a secondary and especially a primary atom. In general, as the amount of paraffin in the raw material increases, the yield increases, that is, it also depends on the chemical composition of naphtha.

The thermal stability of hydrocarbons increases in the series paraffins < naphthene < arenes and decreases with increasing chain length.

The variety of secondary reactions that occur makes process modeling difficult, especially as the nature of the feedstock becomes more complex and the

degree of conversion increases. Until now, experience, empirical dependencies and experimental verification play a very important role during the design of furnaces.

Technological parameters of the process

Thermodynamics and kinetics dictate the following conditions for pyrolysis:

- obtaining the optimal temperature for the type of raw material as soon as possible due to the supply of a significant amount of heat;
- reduction of their partial pressure due to dilution of hydrocarbons with water vapor;
- minimum possible connection time;
- the minimum possible cooling time for pyrolysis gases leaving the reactor.

To achieve them in practice, special furnaces and hardening evaporation apparatus are used, the designs of which are constantly being improved. In general, a pyrolysis plant necessarily consists of two main parts: a “hot” section, where the pyrolysis of raw materials and recycling is carried out, and a “cold” section, which is responsible for product separation and purification (Fig. 2).

Figure 2.

Shows one of the variants of the highly simplified diagram of the "hot" section of the naphtha pyrolysis unit

In the heat exchanger system, the raw material heated at high speed (it can reach 300 m/s and higher at the exit of the furnace) is fed to the inlet of the pipeline, which includes recycling. This mixture is heated in the convection zone (Fig. 2) and mixed with superheated steam due to the temperature of the exhaust gases, and the temperature at the entrance to the reaction zone of the furnace (radiation chamber – Fig. 2 (2)) should not exceed 600 °C to reduce the undesirable rate of cracking in the heating part. By adjusting the temperature of flue gases in the radiation chamber of the furnace where heat transfer is carried out due to the radiation of hot panels, the required temperature gradient is achieved along the length of the coil, ensuring the required speed of the pyrolysis process. At the exit from the furnace, the gases are subjected to rapid cooling – extinguished in a special high-efficiency tube heat. Converters (800 °C and above, dropping to 370-420 °C in hundredths of a second) – quenching evaporation units (QEA). As shown in the diagram, two-stage cooling is possible.

In the first stage (indirect extinguishing) – with water condensate and in the second (direct extinguishing) – with pyrolysis condensate (Fig. 2 (5)).

Then the reaction products (Fig. 2 (6)) enter the primary or primary fractionation section (Fig. 2 (8)), which contains one or more columns. Here, liquid pyrolysis products are divided into fractions, producing gasoline and pyrolysis gas with a high amount of arene (Bp. up to 150 °C) and heavy fraction (Bp. up to 250 °C) after compression (Fig. 2 (9)), is cleaned of hydrogen sulfide and carbon dioxide and dried on zeolites and sent to the "cold" part of the unit.

There are several options for technological design that solve similar problems: of more or less condensed hydrogen to yield ethylene of 99.9 wt. %, propylene with a purity of 95-99.5 wt. %, C₄ fraction containing 25-50 % butadiene and C₅ fraction.

Modern pyrolysis furnaces have vertically arranged coils with multi-gear movement of raw materials.

An increase in productivity is achieved by combining several combustion chambers in one body, where more than ten parallel working coils, sometimes made of pipes of different diameters, are placed. Special tube furnace designs are required to ensure harsh pyrolysis conditions (T above 850 °C, contact time in

tenths of a second).

In recent decades, the development of the process has been focused on increasing its hardness, i.e., looking for possible ways to increase the temperature load and reduce the residence time. Currently, temperatures of ~ 850 °C, contact times of 0.2-0.3, and H₂O/feed mass ratio = 0.5-0 are typically used to achieve ethylene yields of 30 % and higher (in the case of naphtha).

Conclusion

Certain progress has been achieved at the stage of separation of the products of the process, as a result of which individual butenes, iso- and n-amylene, isopentane, isoprene, dicyclopentadiene have become more accessible, which can give a sharp impetus to the development of new industrial syntheses based on them.

References

1. Aleksandrov Yu.A., Tsyganova E.I., Shekunova V.M. i dr. // Zhurn. obshh. himii. 2010. T. 80. Vyp. 4. S. 581-587.
2. Aleksandrov Yu.A., Shekunova V.M., Pishhurova I.A. i dr. // Zhurn. obshh. himii. 2009. T. 79. Vyp. 6. S. 945-950.
3. Gashimov F.A. // Zhurn. prikl. himii. 2009. T. 82. № 5. S. 9-16.
4. Aleksandrov Yu.A., Shekunova V.M., Didenkulova I.I., Pishhurova I.A. // Zhurn. obshh. himii. 2008. T. 78. Vyp. 10. S. 1662-1664.
5. Mirzoyeva L.M., Khalafova I.A. Residual Fuel Oil Cracking Using Alumium Plant Sludges as Catalysts // Chemistry and technology of fuels and oils, 2016, № 5 (597), p. 25-28
6. Mirzoyeva L.M., Andryushchenko N.K., Khalafova I.A. Hydrofining of the heavy fraction of catalytic cracking gasoline, producing from mixture of Azerbaijan oil // ISJ International Scientific Journal Theoretical and Applied Science, Philadelphia, USA, 2018, V. 67, № 11, p. 21-24
7. Khalafova I.A., Ismailova Z.I. Intensification of the catalytic cracking process under the influence of a magnetic field // International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science, Philadelphia, USA, 2021, № 3, V. 95, P. 380-387
8. Khalafova I.A. Research of the composition of gases produced in the catalytic cracking process under the influence of magnetic field // Processes of Petrochemistry and Oil Refining, 2022, V. 23, № 1, P. 61-72